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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Economic Policies in Nigeria 2000 – 2015: An Evaluation of their Efficacy

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Abstract

This study evaluates the success of economic policies in Nigeria between the year 2000 and 2015. Since Nigeria's independence in 1960, several economic policies and programmes have been formulated and implemented to achieve specified macroeconomic objectives. However, the persistence of macroeconomic ills such as the rising cost of living, worrisome unemployment situation and staggering economic growth cast doubts on the effectiveness of these policies; which therefore calls for their evaluation. Specifically, the research evaluates the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) and the Transformation Agenda. The objectives of the study include the assessment of the extent to which NEEDS was successful with respect to wealth creation, employment generation, and poverty reduction, and evaluation of the success of Transformation Agenda with reference to growth and development indicators – GDP growth, inflation rate, unemployment rate and growth in capital formation. Method of analysis adopted is purely descriptive. Empirical results reveal that NEEDS programme failed to achieve its objectives of wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study also reveals that Transformation Agenda failed to stimulate growth in the economy; unemployment and cost of living measured by inflation rate were observed to be higher during the period of Transformation Agenda than in the period before; this was judged to be disappointing given the huge amount of money that has been allocated for its implementation. On the whole, it is concluded that both NEEDS and the Transformation Agenda failed to achieve their objectives. Based on the findings and for the purpose of achieving success in future economic policies and programmes in Nigeria, it is recommended among others, that the problem of poor financial intermediation be addressed through provision of reliable information between borrowers and lenders; ensuring continuity in implementation of government programmes; and holding public office holders accountable on the outcome of government programmes in their trust.

Keywords: Economic policies, NEEDS, Transformation Agenda, Evaluation, Nigeria.

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1. Introduction

Every economy pursues the same macroeconomic objectives; although the priority attached to each of the objectives differs from one country to another depending on the economic conditions and peculiarities of the economy in question. Todaro and Smith (2011) in their analysis of growth diagnostic framework, maintain that different countries face different binding constraints on achieving faster rate of economic growth and development. The three major macroeconomic goals of any economy include price level stability, achieving full employment for her work force as well as attaining faster rate of economic growth and development. To achieve set goals, the formulation and implementation of economic policies becomes imperative.

What then is an economic policy? Economic policies are statements which when put into actions help to steer the economy. Akinyede and Elumah (2017) maintain that economic policies are activities and responses meant to impact the performance of the economy which are consistently implemented and administered by the government. On a wide view, economic policies are formulated and implemented to enhance economic efficiency, improve economic security, promote economic stability (full employment and the control of inflation), and ensure economic growth. Economic policies can be broadly classified into three, namely fiscal policy, monetary policy and trade policies (Adeboyo *et al.*, 2021).

Fiscal policy is a branch of government policy concerned with obtaining revenue through taxes and other means, as well as determining the pattern of spending with the aim of influencing economic activities. The emanation of fiscal policy is traced to the work of Keynes who brought about the idea of fiscal policy during the Great Depression of the 1930s, as a way of reinvigorating growth. Monetary policies on the other hand, are actions by the monetary authorities to influence the national economic outcome by controlling the quantity and direction of money supply. Trade policies are formulated to boost the nation's position in international trade. The trade policies include taxes imposed on import and export, inspection regulations, tariffs and quotas. Trade policies are known as commercial policy or international trade policy since they are directed towards economic transactions across international borders. Monetary policies are often used in combination with fiscal policies and trade policies to influence the direction of the economy and achieve economic goals (Baker *et al.*, 2016).

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Generally, a policy is directed to achieve specific objectives. Nigerian governments over the years in her quest to grow a sustainable economy have embarked on various macroeconomic policy options to achieve specific objectives. The ability of an economy to support a defined level of economic production and the desire for the country to have minimal fluctuations in the macro-economy is a function of the policies of the government and actions of its Central Bank. Nigeria economy dropped into recession in 2016 after more than two decades, showing negative economic shocks, conflicting economic policies, and security problems (African Economic Outlook, 2017). The Nigerian government periodically sets policies as corrective measures for the volatile economy. While the Central Bank of Nigeria develops monetary policies for the financial sector, the Federal Government in conjunction with relevant agencies, formulates other relevant policies for the industries.

The Nigerian economy has faced the problem of excess liquidity, slow growth in gross domestic product (GDP); unpredictable high inflation rate, high unemployment, periodic variation in external reserves, exchange rate inconsistency, yearly budget deficit, high public debts; untapped revenue sources, over dependence on crude oil as a major source of revenue which cause different systems of monetary and fiscal policies to evolve in Nigeria (Musasa, 2012).

Successive governments in Nigeria in an attempt to address the numerous challenges facing the country since independence in 1960 have embarked on development plans. It is noteworthy to emphasize that Nigeria since her independence had adopted and applied four national development plans, namely the First National Development Plan (1962 – 1968); the Second National Development Plan (1970 – 1974); the Third National Development Plan (1975 – 1980) and the Fourth National Development Plan (1981 – 1985). The Fifth National Development plan did not see the light of the day before it was replaced by the perspective plan (1986 – 1990). It suffices to note that the economic reform programmes are expected to be continuous and they require constant fine-tuning and adjustments in tune with unfolding realities in the domestic and international economic environments. The various governments also initiated and implemented specific policies and programmes over the years. These programmes include: Better Life Programme for rural Dwellers (BLP), Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), Family Support Programme (FSP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), National Poverty Eradication Programme

(NAPEP), Agricultural Development Programme (ADP), among others.

Specific policies and programmes that took place between the year 2000 and 2015 include: National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), Seven-Point Agenda, and the Transformation Agenda. The administration of President Yar'adua presented a seven point agenda for development in Nigeria and it was aimed at tackling the numerous problems of power and energy; food security and agriculture; wealth creation and empowerment; transport sector; land reforms, security, and education. However, following the death of President Yar'adua, President Goodluck Jonathan did not continue with the seven-point agenda, he rather came up with the new idea tagged "Transformation Agenda." Despite the formulation and implementation of these programmes, the numerous problems confronting the nation as highlighted earlier persist, casting doubts on the extent to which the goals of some of the programmes have been achieved. The objectives of this study therefore, are to:

- (i) assess the extent to which the objectives of NEEDS have been achieved with respect to wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction;
- (ii) evaluate the success of the Transformation Agenda with respect to growth and development indicator - GDP growth, inflation rate, unemployment rate and growth in capital formation.

2.0 Review of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS)

As a democratic government was elected in Nigeria in May 1999, after many years of military rule, there was a high hope and high expectations among Nigerians that the democratic government will turn the country around and position her to the right direction. The National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) was in two phases. The first phase (NEEDS 1) was a four-year (2003 - 2007) medium term development plan and it was expected to be implemented by all the three tiers of government and other stakeholders including the private sector, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and the general public. The reform programme was premised upon four cardinal goals of Wealth creation, Employment generation, Poverty reduction and Value re-orientation. NEEDS had its counterparts at the state level called SEEDS (State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy) and at the local level as LEEDS (Local Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy) for the 774 local

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governments of the Nigerian federation. At the federal capital territory, it was called FEEDS (Federal Government Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy). NEEDS, SEEDS, LEEDS, and FEEDS were expected to transform the Nigerian economy and drastically reduce poverty through employment creation (Umo, 2012). The long term goals were crafted to provide strategic focus and direction, and inculcate the right ethics, discipline, patriotism, virtues of hard work; honesty, respect for traditional values, entrepreneurial spirit and excellence, and provide incentive structure that rewards and celebrates private enterprise among the citizenry (FGN, 2004).

The National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS 2)

Before the expiration of NEEDS 1 in 2007, the country embarked on the production of NEEDS 2 which was to cover 2008 to 2011. NEEDS 2 emphasized the importance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) for employment generation and technical innovation. The government response had been to set up the Small and Medium Scale Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN). This agency was expected to promote the growth and development of SMEs by developing entrepreneurs and linking them with micro-finance institutions. The central objective of NEEDS 2 was poverty reduction by 30% by the end of the plan cycle in 2011. This was to be accomplished by wealth creation via the process of production. According to Umo (2012), the key areas of production were human capital, physical infrastructure, good governance, macro-economic management, value re-orientation, peace and security and regional development. The strategic framework of NEEDS 2 is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Strategic Framework of NEEDS 2

Source: Adapted from Umo (2012, p.74).

The Transformation Agenda (2011 – 2015)

The government of President Goodluck Jonathan in 2011, initiated a policy tagged Transformation Agenda which was meant to run from 2011 – 2015 and promised to be a policy and programme that will transform Nigeria to an economic powerhouse in the world. A presidential committee tagged Economic Management Team (EMT) was set up consisting of technical experts drawn from both public and private sector (Gyong, 2012). The content of the Transformation Agenda as summarised by the national planning commission focused on infrastructural development, power, economy, energy and gas; security, agriculture and industry; women affairs, water resources, mineral

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resources, education, national questions, reforms, and the Niger Delta. A breakdown of the Transformation Agenda with specific targets in each of the focussed sub-sectors of the economy is shown in Table1. A careful study of Table1 revealed that most of the economic challenges in Nigeria were pinpointed in the Transformation Agenda. The transformation Agenda if well implemented would catapult Nigeria to an enviable height in economic growth and national development as it seeks to revamp ailing industries, reducing poverty through creation of massive employment opportunities and fighting corruption at all levels of governance, deliver stable and constant supply of electricity, reduce importation of generators among others. Therefore, we assess this policy using growth and development indicators such as GDP growth rate, inflation rate, employment rate and growth in capital formation.

2.1 Literature Review

A good number of studies have been conducted on the relationship between economic policies/programmes and macroeconomic performance in both developed and developing countries. Different techniques and approaches are adopted among the scholars in relation to types of data, number of variables and economic conditions of the study area.

Akinyede and Elumah (2017) examined the impact of economic policy on economic stability in Nigeria. They considered monetary, fiscal and trade policies in their study. Economic stability was proxy by GDP growth; fiscal policy was proxy by tax revenue and government debt; monetary policy was proxy by real interest rate and broad money supply, while trade policy was proxy by export and import of goods and services. With the use ARDL approach to co-integration to analyze data 1981-2016, they found that economic policy has a significant effect on economic stability in Nigeria both in the short-run and in the long-run. They therefore, concluded that the usefulness of economic policy cannot be over-emphasized in the pursuit of economic stability in Nigeria.

Akpan and Udofia (2016) examined the effects of economic policies on private consumption expenditure in Nigeria using time series data, covering the period of 1981 to 2014. In order to realise the study objectives, instruments of fiscal and monetary policies were utilised to establish the relationship. The study adopted an OLS technique for estimation and finding revealed that economic policies significantly contributed to

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private consumption and economic growth simultaneously.

Idris *et al.* (2017) evaluated the process and structure of economic policy in Nigeria using a contextual analysis. The aim was to establish a relationship between economic reform policies and economic growth. Using a contextual analysis to demonstrate the casual link, figures were utilised to provide more understanding and clear expression. Result of the study indicated that a favourable macroeconomic environment is essential and desirable for any meaningful and sustainable development. They concluded that economic reform policies have contributed immensely to the sustainable growth and development of the Nigerian economy through the introduction of fiscal discipline and transparency in the management of public resources. They recommended that government should reduce foreign influence in its macroeconomic management of domestic activities; and that policies that have proven to be successful in the long-run must be accorded high priority in order to realise its maximum benefit towards improving social and economic welfare of the citizenry.

Olusegun (2014) examined the effects of macroeconomic policies on agricultural development in emerging and developing countries. To demonstrate how the import policy on agriculture especially in the early phase of development can lead to economic growth, the paper utilised a descriptive analysis to explore both theoretical and empirical evidence.

Alder *et al.* (2013) examined the effects of economic reform and industrial policy on economic growth in China. The study employed a panel of 270 cities from 1988 to 2010 to exploit the variation in establishing different types of zones within the region and to further determine the developmental effects of the said reforms. To estimate the result, a regression analysis was employed using a logarithm transformation of the variables. Finding revealed that economic reform contributes to the increase and growth of real GDP level.

Stillman *et al.* (2008) investigated the long-run impact of structural reforms on local communities in New Zealand, using a census data covering 1986 to 2001. The paper analysed the adjustment process in 140 sampled areas by adopting three constructs, namely employment, population, and housing price as the basis for measuring the impact of structural reform on local communities. Findings from the regression analysis showed that structural reforms in New Zealand have a persistent effects and long-run impact on the local communities.

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Džunić (2006) examined the relationship and interdependency between economic reforms and political liberalisation in the post-socialist transition economies. A contextual approach was adopted to demonstrate the impact economic reforms on political liberalisation. The correlation coefficient between economic growth, the policy of economic reforms and political liberalisation revealed high intensity; implying that countries with the highest index of democratisation also possesses higher growth rates. In particular, there existed a positive development in form of economic growth due to simultaneous interactions of liberalisation measures both in economy and politics.

In the same vein, Chirwa (2005) examined the effects of macroeconomic policies on poverty reduction in Malawi using a panel data from 1998 to 2002. The paper utilised a regression analysis to show evidence on the impact of changes in intermediate policy outcomes in rural areas of Malawi. Findings showed that macroeconomic policies which facilitate and enhance the living standard of the people through provision of job opportunities have the greatest potential in reducing poverty and leads to economic growth.

In another development, Carvalho *et al.* (2013) analyses the impact of reform of economic institutions and infrastructure sectors on the economic, educational and health dimensions of human wellbeing among 25 transition economies. The paper utilised a panel data covering the period of 1992 to 2007 and the regression analysis to measure the effects of reforms packages for the countries under consideration. In general, results showed that reform measures have positive impacts on economic growth, but the effect depends on individual countries as the result revealed a mixed finding.

Furthermore, Staehr (2005) determined the effects of policy reforms on economic growth in 25 transition economies by using a panel data covering the period of 1989 to 2001. Results from the regression output indicated that macroeconomic reforms are essential to economic growth and that policy of liberalisation and small-scale privatisation without structural reforms also contributes to sustainable development in the long-run.

Hill (2013) evaluated the implication of policy reforms within the political economy framework of Asian countries. The study further highlighted factors that appear to be regularly present during significant and durable reform episodes. By adopting an analytical survey of economic policy reforms in Southeast Asia, result

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showed that reforms are essential to economic development particularly when they deliver within the constituency expectations. This implies the need for the reforms to be comprehensive and properly aligned with other sub-sectors of the economy; hence, the implementation process is desirable.

In addition, Kathuria *et al.* (2013) examined the effects of economic reforms on manufacturing dualism in India by taking into cognisance the existence of productivity differentials between informal and formal manufacturing firms. The aim was to identify the technical efficiency levels of formal and informal manufacturing firms and the effects of economic reforms for the given industry. The paper employed a cross-sectional data covering the period 1989 to 2006 and uses a stochastic frontier analysis to find the firm measures of technical efficiency. Findings from the estimation revealed that economic reforms have contributed to the rapid increase of productivity level of manufacturing firms across both the formal and informal sectors.

Nevertheless, Moshi and Kilindo (1999) investigated the effects of government policies on essential macroeconomic indicators in Tanzania. The paper assumed that private sector investment is necessary if meaningful economic growth is to be realised. They maintained that, to attain such milestones and enhance investment level, suitable monetary and fiscal policies need to be designed and implemented, combined with optimal provision of social and economic infrastructures. Result showed that economic policies of Tanzania have contributed immensely to output growth through private investment.

3. Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Results

3.1 NEEDS: Wealth Creation, Employment Generation and Poverty Reduction

There are linkages among wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction. Wealth creation generates employment opportunities and people can only escape poverty by being gainfully employed. We selected certain indices that aid wealth creation and poverty reduction to evaluate the success or otherwise of the NEEDS programme. These indices as shown in Table 2 include manufacturing capacity utilisation (MACU), index of manufacturing production (IMAP), index of mining production (IMIP), index of electricity production (IELP), index of industrial production (IINP), and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF).

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Figure 2: Trend of Unemployment in Nigeria (2000-2011)

Figure 3: Trend of Poverty Headcount in Nigeria (2000-2011)

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Figure 2 is the trend of unemployment in Nigeria from the year 2000 to 2011. Although the NEEDS programme started in 2003, there is need to observe the rate of unemployment in the years prior to its commencement in order to assess how the NEEDS programme has impacted on these variables and the economy at large within the period under study. The unemployment rate in 2002 was 8.8% before the commencement of NEEDS in 2003 when it rose to 10.8%. The rate of unemployment increased further to 10.9% in 2007 which was the terminal period for NEEDS 1. Poverty index (POHC) also rose from 46 to 92.5 within the same period. Figure 3 depicts Nigeria's poverty headcount. The rise in unemployment and poverty within the period may have been attributed to a fall in the manufacturing capacity as reflected in the decline in the index of manufacturing production (IMAP) from 147.9 to 89.2 (see table 1). It should be noted also that between 2003 and 2007, Index of Mining Production (IMIP) declined from 146.6 to 132.7; however, the index of electricity production increased within the period from 148.0 to 190.2. Generally, the total Index of Industrial Production (IINP) declined by 18.6% from 146.7 to 119.4 within the period covered by NEEDS 1. The decline in industrial capacity implies that wealth creation is hampered. We deduce from the above analysis that the performance of NEEDS 1 was far below expectation and unimpressive with regards to wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction.

NEEDS 2 took effect in 2007 before the expiration of NEEDS 1. Unemployment rate increased from 10.9% in 2007 to 12.8% in 2008. Poverty headcount, however, declined from 92.5 to 52.8 within the same period. It is observed from figure 2 and table 2 that while unemployment rate was 8.8% in 2002 before the commencement of the programme, it rose to 14.6% at its termination in 2011. This is the highest rate of unemployment from the year 2000 to 2011. Also, the poverty headcount of 93.5 is much higher than the 48.4 it recorded in 2002 before the commencement of the NEEDS programme in 2003. This scenario results from weak industrial base as reflected in the decline in the index of industrial production from 145.2 in 2002 to 131.9 in 2011. This implies that NEEDS was not a potent programme for wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The failure of the programme may be attributed to some factors. Nigeria's growth experience has failed to be employment-friendly. Employment, though recognised as important in NEEDS programme, had not been made the focus of growth strategy. For instance, NEEDS correctly noted the

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importance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) for employment generation and technical innovation. The government response had been to set up Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN). The agency was expected to promote growth and development of SMEs by developing entrepreneurs and linking them with micro-finance institutions. However, there were some weaknesses in the operation of SMEDAN, especially the ad-hoc approach to entrepreneurship development whereby very short courses were organised for a limited number of entrepreneurs. Also, Umo (2012) noted the issue of weak financial intermediation exhibited by micro-finance banks and charging of high interest rate for profit making to be another impeding factor.

Table 1: Variables for Analysis (NEEDS)

YEAR	UNEM	POHC	MACU	IMAP	IMIP	IELP	IINP	GFCF
2000	11.5	94.1	32.99	138.2	144.3	141.2	138.9	331.06
2001	9.6	92.8	42.70	142.3	144.9	144.6	145.3	372.14
2002	8.8	48.4	45.48	146.3	133.7	146.7	145.2	499.68
2003	10.8	46	45.34	147.9	146.6	147.2	146.7	865.88
2004	10.2	53.5	45.00	145.7	154	148	151.2	863.07
2005	9.4	57.8	47.74	145.8	164.8	291	158.8	804.40
2006	9.9	56.6	48.56	90.3	148.2	205.2	131.2	1546.53
2007	10.9	92.5	62.04	89.2	132.7	190.2	119.4	1936.96
2008	12.8	52.8	53.84	91.2	129.6	198.2	117.8	2053.01
2009	11.2	77.6	55.14	92.4	129.4	198.3	118.2	3050.58
2010	11.54	53.5	56.22	94.2	131.7	200.7	122.1	9183.06
2011	14.6	93.5	55.21	102.5	143.2	202.5	131.9	9897.20

3.2 Transformation Agenda and Macroeconomic Variables

Our aim here is to evaluate the success of the Transformation Agenda with respect to growth and development indicators like GDP growth, inflation rate, unemployment rate, growth in capital formation and so on. In fact, since transformation connotes a complete change, it suffices to expect its effect on the Nigerian economy as a whole. The evaluation is done using figures 4 and 5.

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Figure 4: Multiple Bar Chart Showing GDP growth, Inflation and Unemployment (2010-2015)

Figure 5: GDP Growth (2010-2015)

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It is observed from both figures 4 and 5 that between the period 2010 and 2015, the country recorded the highest GDP growth in 2010. Transformation Agenda programme started in 2011. GDP growth dropped from 7.84% in 2010 to 4.39% in 2011. It dropped further to 4.28% in 2012. GDP growth however, rose from 4.28% in 2012 to 5.39% and 6.31% in 2013 and 2014 respectively. The mean growth rate of GDP within the period covered by Transformation agenda (2011-2015) was 4.7%, which is lower than the 4.84% recorded in 2010. Within the period under review, the least GDP growth of 2.65% was recorded in 2015, the year transformation agenda ended (see table 2). It is deduced from the above analysis that Transformation Agenda policy has failed to stimulate growth in the economy.

Next, we use a multiple bar chart to compare the growth rate of GDP, inflation rate and unemployment rate. The comparison is realistic since the variables are all in rates (see figure 4). The figure shows that for all the years under analysis, the growth in GDP were lower than that of inflation rate and unemployment rate. This suggests that GDP growth within the period may not have been influenced by green investment in the real sector, resulting in a situation of growth without job creation. Also, among the three variables, the growth in unemployment has been the highest throughout the years. This is a clear case of underutilisation of human resources. The low attention given to human resources exerted negative impact on the industrial base and capital formation which in turn retards economic growth and development. The negative relationship between unemployment and GDP growth (economic growth) as postulated in economic development theory is applicable in the Nigerian case (see table 2). We submit that the efficacy of Transformation Agenda is far below expectation given the huge amount of money that has been allocated for its implementation. Appendix 1 shows the sectors in focus and their specific targets during Transformation Agenda while appendix 2 shows the budgetary allocations for their implementations.

Table 2: Variables for the Analysis (Transformation Agenda)

Year	GDPG	INFR	UNEM	MACU	IMAP	IMIP	IELP	IINP	GFCF
2010	7.84	11.8	11.54	56.22	94.2	131.7	200.7	122.1	9183.06
2011	4.89	10.3	14.6	55.21	102.5	143.2	202.5	131.9	9897.20
2012	4.28	12	12.4	54.33	106.6	146.7	206.3	136.9	10281.95
2013	5.39	7.96	12.8	56.34	109.2	146.3	206.4	138	11478.08
2014	6.31	7.98	12.8	58.11	125.2	128.4	187.2	115.9	13595.84
2015	2.65	9.55	13.3	59.91	187.3	131.6	182.4	116.1	14112.17

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study assessed the efficacy of National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) and Transformation Agenda programmes in Nigeria at meeting their objectives. The extent to which the objectives of NEEDS have been achieved with respect to wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction has been examined. Also, the success of the Transformation Agenda with respect to growth and development indicator - GDP growth, inflation rate, unemployment rate and growth in capital formation has been examined. NEEDS is concluded to have performed far below expectation in terms of wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction in Nigeria, and this failure of the programme may be attributed to some factors. Nigeria's growth experience has failed to be employment-friendly. Though employment was recognised as important in NEEDS programme, it was not made the focus of growth strategy. The government response had been to set up Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), and it was expected to promote growth and development of SMEs by developing entrepreneurs and linking them with micro-finance institutions. However, there were some weaknesses in the operation of SMEDAN, especially the ad-hoc approach to entrepreneurship development whereby very short courses were organised for a limited number of entrepreneurs. Also, the issue of weak financial intermediation exhibited by micro-finance banks and the charging of high interest rate for profit making was another hindrance Umo (2012) noted.

Transformation Agenda policy has failed to stimulate growth in the economy since the growth in GDP within the period had been very low compared to the period before the implementation of the policy. Unemployment and cost of living measured by inflation rate were observed to be higher during the period of the Transformation Agenda than in the period before. The efficacy of Transformation Agenda is judged to be far below expectation, given the huge amount of money that was allocated for its implementation (see appendix 1). The conclusion of the study is that both NEEDS and the Transformation Agenda have failed in terms of achieving their set objectives. Based on the findings and for the purpose of achieving success in future economic programmes in Nigeria, the following recommendations are offered:

- (I) The problem of poor financial intermediation should be addressed through the provision of reliable information between borrowers and lenders. Poor financial

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intermediation was one of the weaknesses of SMEDAN and this affected the success of SMEs.

- (ii) There should be continuity in the implementation of government programmes. The exit of a government should not mark the end of a laudable government programme.
- (iii) Public office holders should be sincere about implementing government policies; they should be held accountable on the outcome of government programmes in their thrust. Government should be sincere about fighting corruption in the country.

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Elevis Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

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